

Evolution of Students' Astronomy Career Interests: A Gender Study

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Abstract

This thesis uses survey data (n=15,847) to characterize the evolution of student interest in an astronomy career in the period between middle school and the beginning of college. We find that middle school students have a relatively high interest in astronomy, which sharply declines with every phase of their education. However, many of the students who leave astronomy - particularly male students - feed heavily into other STEM disciplines. Through statistical modeling, we find that students who spend extracurricular time observing stars and/or talking to their family and peers about science are significantly more likely to hold an interest in pursuing astronomy at the end of high school. We also find that females who observe stars show a more drastic improvement in their odds of pursuing astronomy than males do. Furthermore, we find that these outside-of-school time activities are better predictors of astronomy interest than commonly studied academic predictors. We discuss the implications of these findings on future extracurricular programming for students.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Women in STEM

In a world of relentlessly advancing information and technology, the need for quality scientists and engineers is constantly growing. The improvement of science and mathematics education is crucial to sustaining and strengthening national innovation and research capabilities. Moreover, at present, the nation is subject to an undeniable gender gap in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM), starting as early as middle school and extending through to the professional world. In 2007 and 2010 publications, the National Academy of Science (NAS) declared a significant demand for more STEM workers, while also entreating the fulfillment of female potential in academic science and engineering. The field of astronomy is of particular interest: for a discipline studying the enormity of the universe, the world of professional astronomy is quite small in numbers. Yet astronomy plays a much larger role in popular science (TV, movies, science fiction novels) than most other STEM fields, giving many young students an initial curiosity about the subject. It is therefore important to investigate both the factors that affect the retention of astronomy students, and how the increase of astronomy students may affect the STEM workforce as a whole. That being said, the proper methods by which to increase STEM interest of any kind are still under debate, as researchers are currently at work to determine the primary factors attracting and deterring STEM students, and when these factors come into play.

The often-used metaphor of a “leaky pipeline” illustrates a common trend in STEM education: even though young children begin their educations with high interest levels in STEM fields, this interest diminishes at every phase of their education, with accelerated loss of female students (Riegle-Crumb, Moore, & Ramos-Wada, 2010; Sadler et al., 2011). This is a supply-side model. It suggests that if more women enter the pipeline early on we will increase numbers on the other end. This can often over-simplify the problem. For example,

female students' rates of departure from STEM differ across various STEM disciplines, and it is therefore important to determine where the largest gender disparities lie in order to target their causes.

Careers in medicine and health have a particularly even gender distribution. These careers also exhibit numerous qualities distinguishing them from other science disciplines, so much so that they need not be included within the umbrella term “STEM” for the purposes of this study, but will rather be addressed as “STEM-related” fields. On the other end of the spectrum, it has been found that the most noteworthy gaps in female persistence during high school occur in astronomy and computer science (Sadler et al., 2011). Similarly, the 2012 Bayer Facts of Science Education survey found that computer science and mathematics chairs reported low efficacy on behalf of their institutions regarding retaining and graduating female STEM students. This survey did not, however, consider the field of astronomy. Numerous researchers have already studied the gender gaps in computer science (Bayer Corp., 2012; Cheryan et al., 2003; Lagesen, 2007; Margolis, Fisher, & Miller, 2000; Singh et al., 2005) and mathematics (Dar-Nimrod & Heine, 2006; Guberman, 2004; Pagni, 2002) in recent years, but there is a dearth of knowledge on factors that affect the retention of astronomy students, particularly with respect to gender.

One publication on the retention of female astronomers was included in the Symposium on Astronomy Education in May 1976. The article posited that female astronomers experience a lack of opportunity at the university level due to discrimination and “educational sex-role stereotyping”, and supported these claims through interviews (Rauscher, 1976). This study, which was published almost 40 years ago, is largely anecdotal in nature. Since this publication, little progress has been made in this line of inquiry. In 1992, Barlow et al. published *Women in Astronomy: A Sample of Issues and Ideas*, primarily discussing issues that female astronomers encounter during their careers with little reference to what goes on during their education. Other publications of this sort have followed, leaving a grave defi-

ciency of information on factors that influence male and female astronomy students before they declare a college major.

1.2 History of Women in Astronomy

The historical saga of women in astronomy is distinct from other STEM disciplines. Unlike most sciences, which began as entirely male-dominated fields and subsequently incorporated the work of female professionals over time, many important early achievements in astronomy were accomplished by women. As early as 1847, Maria Mitchell became the first person to observe a comet invisible to the naked eye, and was given an international award by the King of Denmark. In the 1890s, when more women began to venture from their traditional roles as wives and mothers and enter the workplace, many women came to the Harvard College Observatory (HCO) to work under HCO Director Edward Charles Pickering as “computers”. This work was thought more acceptable for women as it involved the invisible service work skills often associated with secretarial work and femininity. (Rossiter, 1997) Pickering did not anticipate that these women, including the famous Henrietta Leavitt, Williamina Fleming, and Annie Jump Cannon, would make many pivotal developments in astronomy at the time by reviewing astronomical images printed on glass plates. These developments include the establishment of the modern stellar classification system and analysis of Cepheid variable stars (“The History of Women in Astronomy”).

Soon thereafter, Cecilia Payne-Gaposchkin became the first person, male or female, to receive a Ph.D. for work done at the HCO in 1925, and later became the first female professor and Chair of Harvard’s Astronomy Department in 1956 (“The History of Women in Astronomy”). In fact, 4 of the first 7 Ph.D.s in astronomy from Harvard were granted to females, occurring in the 7 years between 1925 and 1932. However, during the following 7 years, Harvard graduated 19 male Astronomy Ph.D.s and only 1 female. Throughout the 1950s, the NSF estimated less than 10% of American astronomers to be female (Rossiter, 1997).

Furthermore, despite modern progress, only 11 out of 39 Astronomy Ph.D.s from Harvard have been female in the last five years (“Astronomy Alumni”). Despite the fact that female astronomers got off to such a positive start around the turn of the century, women are at present a definite minority. It is the goal of this study to investigate factors that can reverse this loss of female astronomers and encourage an increase in astronomy students, both male and female.

1.3 Call to Action

According to former Harvard University President Lawrence Summers, the underrepresentation of women in STEM is likely due to “issues of intrinsic aptitude” rather than discrimination. In a 2005 speech, Summers stated “if there was really a pervasive pattern of discrimination that was leaving an extraordinary number of high-quality potential candidates behind, one suspects that in the highly competitive academic marketplace there would be more examples of institutions that succeeded substantially by working to fill the gap.” (Sumner, 2005) Not only is this stance highly controversial, but in the case of astronomy it is also strongly disputed by historical evidence. History has seen female astronomers thrive and contribute pivotal discoveries to the field, and yet in modern culture there seem to be external factors inhibiting the engagement of female students with the study of astronomy. Moreover, there is a general lack of interest in astronomy on the part of both female and male students - a phenomenon that has gone unexamined. It is the goal of this study to contribute to filling these gaps in the field of astronomy by examining various effects on students’ persevering interest in astronomy including out-of-school time activities, math and science background, and gender.

2 Literature Review

2.1 The Gender Gap in STEM Education

In recent decades, science education researchers have increasingly analyzed the STEM gender disparity. Researchers at present are conflicted over issues such as the importance of pedagogical choices, extracurricular activities, family involvement, and access to resources. One hypothesized cause of the deficiency in female scientists is that women tend to prefer careers that are more people-oriented and conflict less with family life and personal needs (Diekman et al., 2010; Sadler et al., 2011). Other researchers believe that this gender gap is primarily due to a lack of opportunities, support, and equity for female scientists, rather than an inherent preference of females towards the stereotypical lifestyles of non-STEM fields (Xu, 2008).

One of the largest debates at play is that over the relative influence of pedagogical choices vs. outside of school time (OST) activities on ignition and retention of students' STEM interests. On the pedagogical dispute over depth vs. breadth of study, it has been shown that depth of scientific study has many more positive and lasting effects on students' performance in later science courses, and yet this finding is nearly impossible to implement in classrooms due to the breadth-oriented nature of American standardized tests (Schwartz et al., 2008). In this case, students may find the depth of study they are missing in the classroom through participation in OST science activities. This notion aligns well with conclusions made by Tai et al. (2006), who declare "encouragement of interest and exposure to the sciences should not be ignored in favor of an emphasis on standardized test preparation". With these findings in mind, there is a demand for research on the efficacy of OST activities in encouraging student engagement with science for both males and females.

Furthermore, according to a 2012 study by Riegle-Crumb et al., absolute levels of math and science achievement in school are poor predictors of the persistent gender gap, as female

students tend to have a higher math and science GPA in high school than male students. These results agree with a 2005 report from the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP), which state that over time both boys and girls are taking more math and science courses in high school, and that girls on average have higher math and science GPAs. Moreover, in a longitudinal study by Tai et al. (2006), eighth graders who predicted a STEM career for themselves at age 30 were 1.9 times as likely as their peers to pursue one later in life, suggesting that it may be inherent interest and not performance that most influences students' STEM pursuits. This suggests the possibility that students who persist in science-related OST activities may have a higher interest in related STEM careers, and yet no studies have yet been conducted to test this possibility. Furthermore, although some modern researchers posit that math and science preparation and achievement in school are poor predictors of STEM continuance, such factors are critical control variables in any inquiry of STEM persistence.

In further examination of the STEM gender gap, Hazari et al. (2013) published the results of a study testing five common hypotheses on the retention of female students' STEM career interests throughout high school and early college. This study used data from the Persistence Research in Science and Engineering (PRiSE) survey ($n = 7,505$), and concluded that the discussion of underrepresentation of women in science had a significant positive effect on the female students' persisting interest, whereas there was no noticeable effect from the presence of female science teachers, guest speakers, single-sex classrooms, or the discussion of the work of female scientists. This suggests that female STEM students are not in need of different classroom structures or more female role models, but rather that they need to be able to associate their personal identity with a STEM identity, which can be accomplished through activities such as concrete discussion of the underrepresentation of women in STEM. This is supported by findings showing that women with higher gender rejection sensitivity (a measure of tendency to perceive social-identity threat) experience larger self-

reported instability in “gender-STEM compatibility” during their freshman year of college (Ahlqvist, 2013).

In a related 2010 study by Hazari et al., a survey of 3,829 students from 34 randomly selected universities was analyzed to explore how the concept of a student’s “physics identity” affects their pursuit of a physics career. In this study, the components of a student’s identity were compartmentalized into personal identity, social identity, and identification with physics. The physics identity component included recognition by others, belief in ability to perform, interest/curiosity, and belief in ability to understand. Females’ physics identity was found to be higher for those who discussed female underrepresentation, as it prompted the students to reassess their own biases and predispositions. As Hazari et al. found such significant effects stemming from the discussion of the underrepresentation of women in science, our current study will specifically analyze the effect that talking with family and peers about science has on STEM student retention, among other factors.

It is noteworthy, however, that for females and males in the same physics classroom, the females were significantly less likely to report that the class focused on conceptual understanding, currently relevant science topics, or the benefits of becoming a physicist, although all of these factors positively affected the physics identities of male and female students alike (Hazari et al., 2010). This difference in perception between male and female students inside the classroom is one good reason why researchers have begun to shift their focus to OST activities, where students have an opportunity to cultivate their STEM identity independent of classroom factors.

This discrepancy in pedagogical perception by gender complicates the study of the importance of middle school in establishing and solidifying student STEM interest. Providing middle school students with interactive and authentic scientific experiences in has been shown to help them internalize persevering interest in STEM (Christensen et al., 2006). An additional study by Christensen et al. (2014) showed that although girls reported signifi-

cantly ($p < .05$) lower “semantic perceptions” of STEM careers than boys when surveyed in the beginning of sixth grade, participation in programs which encouraged a self-directed, multidisciplinary science education eliminated this difference such that by the end of sixth grade there was no noticeable distinction between boys’ and girls’ perceptions of STEM as a career. Furthermore, the students who participated in these self-directed programs retained their newfound perceptions throughout two years of follow-up surveys.

In a similar vein, a 2011 study on the PRiSE data by Sadler et al. determined that the key factor influencing a student’s interest in STEM at the end of high school was their interest level at the beginning of high school, extending the tangible longitudinal effects established by Dabney et al. (2011) and Christensen et al. (2006, 2014) with respect to elementary and middle school interest. This effect, however, was weaker for female students, as there was “both a lower retention of STEM career interest among females and a greater difficulty in attracting females to STEM fields during high school” (Sadler et al., 2011). These findings inform our decision to focus most analyses around the transition from the beginning of high school (BHS) to the end of high school (EHS).

In 2012, the Bayer Corporation commissioned a survey of 413 STEM department chairs at America’s top 200 research universities to discuss the state of female and underrepresented minority STEM students at the undergraduate level. When asked about pre-college academic preparation, department chairs on average believed female students 8% more likely to have adequate STEM preparation when compared to males of majority race. If this is true, and academic preparation is not the primary factor deterring female students from STEM, there may be strong factors at play outside of the classroom.

2.2 The STEM Gender Gap Beyond the Classroom

Although the importance of elementary and middle school students’ STEM identity has been established in numerous studies, the implementation of positive change is a challenging

proposition, particularly for female students. One major barrier in elevating girls' physics identity is that female students feel overall less welcome in science-related OST clubs and activities than males (Sadler et al., 2011). In fact, students as young as fourth through sixth grade already have preconceived notions of physical sciences as male-oriented (Potvin et al., 2009). This begs the question of when and how these gendered social expectations arise, and how they can be prevented. We see evidence of such expectations present even in single-sex OST activities not specifically related to science, such as the Boy Scouts and Girl Scouts of America. In these clubs, subtle syntactic differences trigger the gendering of certain subjects. The Boy Scouts tend to present badges with career-oriented or technical syntax, whereas the Girl Scout badges have more whimsical connotations: "Environmental Science" for the Boy Scouts becomes "Flowers" for the Girl Scouts, "Oceanography" becomes "Water", and – as relevant to our research – "Astronomy" becomes "Sky" (Boy Scouts of America, 2014; Girl Scouts of America, 2014).

The effect of socially gendering science topics leaves a lasting impression. In a study of 30 female STEM faculty members at Midwestern University, Rhoton (2011) analyzes the ways in which women in STEM academia enforce gender practices on each other, specifically by encouraging other female scientists to exhibit more stereotypically masculine behavior and refrain from taking part in feminist activism. This article also brings to light questions as to why certain women do not (or claim not to) perceive gender discrimination in STEM despite an abundance of empirical evidence, possibly due to the long-standing social gendering of science careers.

In a study on the ways in which rejection sensitivity undermines the success of female scientists, Ahlqvist, London, & Rosenthal (2013) note that women are more likely to decide later in their education that they want to pursue STEM, while men are more likely to maintain an interest in STEM from early on. The article presents the idea that women who have recently converted to a pursuit of STEM fields may be looking to their environment

for cues of belonging or failure. Any incompatibility between workplace expectations and their personal identity can therefore become a major deterrent. Similarly, in a 2003 study on female computer scientists, Cheryan et al. investigate how stereotypes of a field drive how men and women express interest differently. In this experimental study, researchers put 52 non-computer science majors in 2 different environments: one decorated in a manner stereotypical of computer science majors, and one decorated with generic workplace items. Perhaps unsurprisingly, the female test subjects proved less likely to feel welcome and comfortable in the stereotypical computer science environment than in the other due to its masculine-oriented nature. Additionally, in a longitudinal study of 294 female students at 34 post-secondary schools, Szelenyi and Inkelas (2010) found that “visiting the work setting of a professional in [female] students’ intended field decreased the probability of planning to attend graduate school in STEM by 10.2%”. These studies reveal the lasting implications of establishing female STEM identity early on, and serve as evidence that the gender gap in STEM cannot be attributed to classroom phenomena alone. On the contrary, as students determine their personal STEM identity and interests (or lack thereof), they are being strongly influenced by social interactions and activities outside of school as well as pedagogical choices. For these reasons, it is important that we continue to analyze how and when certain OST activities contribute to student interest in STEM in order to combat the country’s want of scientists and engineers.

2.3 Examining the Efficacy of OST Activities

According to Bergin (1996), OST activities such as sports, art, and other hobbies are surprisingly important in building students’ academic skills. They provide a unique opportunity for students to self-regulate their learning and explore their own intrinsic motivations, helping them make more informed decisions about their future professions. However, although this study successfully concluded that certain OST activities correlate positively to increased

interest in school, improved learning strategies, and better grades overall, this survey was limited in not only scope (only 210 students from one school were surveyed) but also in inquiry, as it focused only on OST activities that built skills directly applicable to classroom functionality. Examples of these activities include note taking, underlining texts, and keeping records of one's progress. Bergin calls for future researchers to examine a larger number of alternative hobbies such as photography, car repair, and computers.

In a 2004 study examining the comparative effects of OST activities on mathematical performance of Latin American and Korean American middle school students, Guberman found that everyday activities, as opposed to intentional pedagogy, produce a kind of informal knowledge that allows children to better interpret and understand mathematics in school. He states that "children's developing knowledge of mathematics reflects the activities in which they participate and the cultural tools (e.g., numbers systems, algorithms) used in them". One major component contributing to the acquisition of these "cultural tools" is the parents' attitudes or beliefs about their children's inherent abilities. However, this study only compared these effects for two ethnic groups, and neglected the effects of students' genders. Also, like Bergin, Guberman used a narrow definition of OST activities, extending only to include activities performed with the active intention of improving classroom skills, such as counting money or comparing object quantities. This void suggests that it is now important to broaden future research to include OST activities associated less directly with didactic advantage, such as those performed for student enjoyment (taking care of animals, playing video games, etc.) and those involving interpersonal interaction (science competitions and clubs, talking to family and peers about science, etc.).

This interpersonal aspect of OST activities in particular is hypothesized to have a strong positive effect on female scientists. As France Anne Cordova of Pennsylvania State University once reported,

Women need encouragement, and this encouragement has to start at home; par-

ents need to value a science career for their daughters. Approval is a very important part of most young women's lives – approval and self-esteem. We find that a little encouragement helps build the self-confidence needed to get over some barriers. The best encouragement, though, is from one's peers, be they male or female. (Barlow, 1992)

Since classroom environments often fail to provide individual support and encouragement to all students, OST activities may provide the environment students need to build their scientific self-confidence through free communication and encouragement.

In fact, in a 2011 study, Dabney et al. found that some of the principal factors affecting students' university interest in STEM include OST science activities, middle school interest in science and mathematics, and gender. However, this study was limited by the inability to determine if the students' STEM interests were a result of or precursor to participation in OST activities, leaving room for further research on the specific effects of OST activities at different ages. Our study therefore sets out to examine the effects of out-of-school time activities on students' persevering interest in STEM fields.

In addition, it is important to note that an analysis of this scale on the effect of OST activities on astronomy career interest does not exist in the literature. A handful of astronomy education journals exist and have existed in the past, such as the *Astronomy Education Review*, but most of its publications focused on classroom pedagogical theory (Duncan et al., 2012; Miller & James, 2011; Rudolph, 2013), classroom activities (Fitzgerald et al., 2011; Lawler, 2013; Sanders et al., 2012), or student misconceptions (Bailey et al., 2012; Calderon-Canales et al., 2013; Sugarman et al., 2011). Detailed reviews of this literature are given by Bishop (2002) and Lelliot & Rollnick (2009). In these publications, little to no attention is given to outside of school time activities other than visiting planetaria. Furthermore, these studies do not examine the effect of student experiences on students' career choices. This informs our decision to analyze the effects of OST activities on astronomy career interest.

3 Data and Methods

The data for this thesis come from the “Outreach Programs and Science Career Intentions” (OPSCI) study (n=15,847), funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF #1161052). They were collected through a large survey administered in the fall term of 2013 to incoming students at a sample of U.S. institutions of higher education that participated the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Talent Expansion Program (STEP) of the National Science Foundation. The STEP program supported initiatives geared toward increasing the number of students receiving associate or baccalaureate degrees in the STEM fields. The survey was administered in freshman English courses, a typical general education requirement for all students - or in similar generally required courses - to gain a representative sample of both STEM and non-STEM students at each participating institution.

In the typical cases, personalized recruitment emails were sent to the Chairs of the English Department, specifically mentioning the STEP researcher involved at their university. Of the 150 institutions, 104 never responded to repeated inquiries. Of the 46 that responded, 27 (59%) participated with at least one professor. This included 23 four-year institutions and 4 two-year institutions. Of the 535 instructors who initially agreed to administer the survey, 414 instructors (77%) followed through, returning 15,847 completed student surveys. The surveys were administered in hardcopy during class time so that student participation was close to 100%.

The questions of the OPSCI survey were to a considerable portion identical with the questions that had already been developed and successfully used in an earlier study titled “Persistence Research in Science and Engineering” (PRiSE; NSF #0624444). Other questions were created specifically for the OPSCI survey by the project team. The OPSCI survey was pilot tested with students at a Southern university. Test-retest reliability of the survey was established by administering the survey to 57 students at that same university twice, in

an interval of about two weeks. For continuous variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient between the test and retest answers served as a measure of reliability; for categorical variables, Cohen's kappa was used. The overall means were 0.73 for the correlation coefficients, and 0.59 for the Cohen's kappas.

4 Descriptive Statistics

Our analyses revolve primarily around three questions in the OPSCI survey. Question 1 asks students to indicate any career interests they had in middle school (MS), the beginning of high school (BHS), the end of high school (EHS), and college (Col). In the survey, students could indicate specific interest in any of 9 different engineering careers, which we modified in our analysis to one unified engineering interest variable. Question 16 asked the students' interest and participation in STEM-related OST activities. Students could select as many activities as they wanted for the following stages in their education: kindergarten through fourth grade, fifth through eighth grade, ninth, tenth, eleventh, and twelfth grades. Question 26 was gender – 50.7% of respondents self-identified as female, 38.7% self-identified as male, and 10.6% failed to specify. Due to the unequal distribution of male and female students in the sample, our analysis is based on percentages rather than absolute numbers of students interested in any given activity or field. Moreover, this thesis considers gender on a binary scale due to the nature of the data set and the formatting of OPSCI Question 26.

Regarding Question 1, we began by examining the overall trends of interest in any given career over time (table shown in Figure 1, graph shown in Figure 2), and then examined the difference in career interest over time with respect to gender (table shown in Figure 3, graph shown in Figure 4). Astronomy interest is shown in red in both plots, and experiences the most extreme and constant decrease of all fields in question. The decrease is stronger for females, although present for male students as well. We also compare interest in STEM,

non-STEM, and STEM-related (Health/Medicine) fields by gender in Figures 5 and 6.

	MS	BHS	EHS	College
Art	8.2%	6.8%	5.6%	4.9%
Astronomy	2.2%	1.1%	0.5%	0.3%
Biology	2.7%	2.9%	2.1%	1.9%
Business	3.3%	6.0%	10.5%	11.8%
Chemistry	0.7%	1.1%	1.1%	0.8%
Comp Sci	2.0%	2.8%	3.3%	3.2%
Earth Science	1.5%	1.4%	1.4%	1.2%
Engineering	3.6%	5.1%	5.7%	5.3%
English	2.0%	2.4%	2.1%	1.8%
Health	5.2%	8.2%	9.7%	9.7%
Law	6.0%	4.9%	3.2%	2.5%
Math	0.8%	1.0%	0.9%	0.8%
Math Teacher	1.7%	1.2%	0.9%	0.7%
Medicine	18.2%	14.6%	12.5%	11.6%
Other	7.2%	6.8%	7.3%	8.5%
Other Science	1.0%	0.9%	0.9%	1.0%
Physics	0.5%	0.8%	0.7%	0.5%
Science Teacher	0.7%	0.6%	0.5%	0.4%
Social Science	1.5%	3.3%	4.5%	4.3%
Sports	7.7%	5.6%	3.9%	3.2%
Teacher	5.1%	4.4%	4.5%	4.2%

Figure 1: Table showing percent of students who indicated some level of interest in specified careers in middle school (MS), the beginning of high school (BHS), the end of high school (EHS), or their freshman year of college. Male and female data are combined.

Further data visualization and graphical analysis was performed on the Question 1 data in the form of inflow and outflow mapping. This is shown in a series of Sankey diagrams, which are traditionally used in engineering to depict energy flow. Inflow maps demonstrate which fields astronomy students are interested in before they decide to pursue astronomy. Outflow maps, on the other hand, reveal which fields astronomy students commonly enter if they choose to leave astronomy. Eight Sankey diagrams are shown below in Figures 7 through 14. Figures 7 and 8 show inflows into astronomy for male and female students, respectively, and Figures 9 and 10 are the corresponding outflow diagrams. Figure 11 is an inflow diagram for all students in the data set, and Figure 12 is the respective outflow diagram. Figures 13 and 14 show the quantities of male vs. female students following any given path in a side-by-side comparison, with Figure 13 showing inflows and Figure 14 showing outflows.

	Female				Male			
	MS	BHS	EHS	College	MS	BHS	EHS	College
Art	10.9%	8.1%	6.4%	5.3%	5.3%	5.5%	5.2%	4.7%
Astronomy	1.6%	0.9%	0.4%	0.2%	3.3%	1.4%	0.7%	0.5%
Biology	2.9%	3.3%	2.5%	2.1%	2.7%	2.7%	1.8%	1.8%
Business	2.5%	5.0%	8.9%	9.9%	4.6%	7.9%	13.3%	15.0%
Chemistry	0.6%	1.0%	1.0%	0.7%	1.0%	1.4%	1.4%	1.1%
Comp Sci	0.6%	1.0%	1.0%	1.0%	3.9%	5.3%	6.4%	6.2%
Earth Science	1.4%	1.6%	1.5%	1.1%	1.7%	1.4%	1.5%	1.4%
Engineering	1.8%	3.4%	4.4%	4.2%	13.4%	18.4%	20.5%	18.8%
English	2.6%	3.1%	2.7%	2.3%	1.5%	1.7%	1.6%	1.5%
Health	8.0%	12.5%	14.9%	14.8%	2.1%	3.8%	4.1%	4.1%
Law	7.0%	5.6%	3.3%	2.5%	5.2%	4.4%	3.2%	2.6%
Math	0.6%	0.9%	0.8%	0.7%	1.1%	1.2%	1.1%	0.9%
Math Teacher	2.5%	1.7%	1.3%	0.9%	0.9%	0.7%	0.7%	0.5%
Medicine	23.8%	19.0%	15.8%	14.8%	12.7%	10.5%	9.1%	8.3%
Other	6.8%	6.9%	7.5%	9.2%	8.4%	7.4%	7.7%	8.2%
Other Science	0.9%	1.0%	1.0%	1.1%	1.2%	1.0%	1.0%	1.0%
Physics	0.3%	0.4%	0.4%	0.2%	0.8%	1.5%	1.4%	1.1%
Science Teacher	0.8%	0.5%	0.5%	0.4%	0.5%	1.5%	0.5%	0.4%
Social Science	2.2%	5.1%	6.6%	6.0%	0.6%	1.3%	2.4%	2.6%
Sports	3.4%	2.9%	2.7%	2.3%	13.8%	9.2%	5.5%	4.3%
Teacher	8.6%	6.8%	6.6%	6.4%	1.5%	1.9%	2.2%	1.9%

Figure 3: Table showing percent of students interested in specified careers in MS, BHS, EHS, and college analyzed separately for males and females.

peers about science - was intentionally left as a solitary factor despite relatively high correlation due to its potential independent impact as suggested by Hazari et al. (2013). A table of each abbreviated variable label and its corresponding activity can be found in Figure 16. These factors will come into play in the statistical modeling of the data in Section 5.2.

We also performed an analysis of interest in each of the 13 OST activities over time with respect to gender. The complete results are shown in Figure 17, with simplified results in Figure 18. These graphs depict the percent of males who participated in a given OST activity versus the percent of females. Since neither axis represents time, the point on each line indicating K-4 interest levels is denoted by a triangle with a back outline, and the points indicating grade 12 interest levels are denoted by a circle with a black outline. The points in between follow chronologically. From these graphs, we see that several activities are skewed towards one gender, or become skewed as students age. An example of this occurs with students who talk to their peers and family about science. As students age, this activity

Figure 4: Log percent of students interested in specified careers in MS, BHS, EHS, and college analyzed separately for males and females. Astronomy interest is shown in red in both graphs and shows an exponential decrease in interest for both genders over time. Females experience a stronger decrease.

Percent of Interested Students Who Identify as Female				
	MS	BHS	EHS	College
Astronomy	31%	34%	32%	23%
STEM	29%	27%	26%	25%
STEM-Rel	63%	64%	64%	65%
Non-STEM	48%	48%	48%	47%

Figure 5: Table showing the percent of students interested in astronomy, STEM, STEM-related (Health/Medicine), or non-STEM fields who identify as female, presented for MS, BHS, EHS, and College. STEM-related fields (Health and Medicine) have the highest percentage of females engaged (64%) while STEM and astronomy remain low at 30% female.

gets increasingly skewed towards male participation. This is particularly troubling in light of previous research done by Hazari et al. (2013) which indicate that discussion of the underrepresentation of women in science is one of the key factors encouraging girls to pursue STEM careers.

Figure 6: Percent of students interested in STEM, non-STEM, and STEM-related (Health/Medicine) fields in MS, BHS, EHS, and College who identify as female. Females are noticeably less interest in STEM and astronomy than males are at all educational stages.

Figure 7: Astronomy inflow diagrams for male students spanning middle school (MS), the beginning of high school (BHS), the end of high school (EHS), and the freshman year of college (College). Path color-coding is executed as follows: red indicates students who retain interest in astronomy, yellow indicates students who come from other STEM fields into astronomy, green indicates students who come from STEM-related fields into astronomy, and blue indicates all other paths to astronomy. It is notable that the overall inflow of students into astronomy decreases as students get older, and that the preponderance of students coming into astronomy are coming from other STEM fields.

Figure 8: Inflow diagrams for female students spanning the same age range as Figure 7. Path color-coding is maintained. This diagram reveals that a very small percentage of students interested in astronomy at any given point in their education maintain that interest through to the next phase. Once again, a large portion of the students coming into astronomy are coming from other STEM fields. In comparison to the male students in Figure 7, this diagram shows fewer students interested in astronomy across the board.

Figure 9: Outflow diagrams for male students. Path color-coding is executed as follows: red indicates students who retain interest in astronomy, yellow indicates students who leave astronomy and go into other STEM fields, green indicates students who leave for STEM-related fields, and blue indicates all other paths out of astronomy. Large outflow paths occur consistently from astronomy to other STEM fields, suggesting that early astronomy interest may feed into later STEM careers preferentially.

Figure 10: Outflow diagrams for female students. Path color-coding is maintained from Figure 9. In comparison to Figure 9, there is less of a preferential outflow of female astronomy students into other STEM fields, with instead a large outflow into non-STEM fields at every stage.

Figure 11: Inflows for all students (male and female combined). Path color-coding is maintained from Figure 7. Because there were more female survey participants than male participants, the path weights in the diagram are determined by the *percent* of male and female students on any given path, rather than the absolute number as used in Figures 7 to 10. For both genders the overall inflow of students into astronomy decreases as students age.

Figure 12: Outflows for all students (male and female combined). Path color-coding is maintained from Figure 9. This diagram supports prior outflow diagrams, revealing that a very small percentage of students interested in astronomy at any given point in their education maintain that interest through to the next phase. Once again, a preponderance of these students leave astronomy in favor of another STEM field.

Figure 13: Inflows for male students vs. female students. Male students are indicated in light blue, female students in pink. These patterns somewhat similar, although not identical.

Figure 14: Outflows for male students vs. female students. Male students are indicated in light blue, female students in pink. We see that more male students flow from astronomy to other STEM fields, and more female students flow from astronomy to non-STEM fields. This pattern holds across all educational stages.

	D1	D2	D3	D4
animalBHS	0.051	0.187	0.163	0.354
chemBHS	0.277	0.219	0.132	0.214
compBHS	0.467	0.053	0.110	0.067
gameBHS	0.063	0.325	0.358	0.104
groupBHS	0.594	0.065	0.080	0.107
nonficBHS	0.236	0.140	0.604	0.212
plantBHS	0.169	0.096	0.113	0.649
progBHS	0.228	0.177	0.140	0.045
scifiBHS	0.151	0.144	0.697	0.123
starBHS	0.282	0.141	0.154	0.269
talkBHS	0.308	0.155	0.359	0.243
tinkeBHS	0.153	0.687	0.128	0.120
tinkmBHS	0.105	0.571	0.153	0.199

Figure 15: Factor analysis table for the 13 OST activities examined in the OPSCI survey. The table shown was generated by analyzing participation in grades 9–10, and was deemed representative of factor analyses performed for grades K–4, 5–8, and 11–12 as well. High correlation is shown highlighted in orange and occurs between taking care of animals & planting seeds/collecting nature things; tinkering with mechanical and/or electrical devices; participation in science groups, clubs, and/or competitions; and reading/watching fictional or non-fiction science and/or playing video games. The following activities were determined to exist as factors by themselves: engaging in chemistry; writing computer programs and/or web pages; talking to family and peers about science; and observing stars.

Label	Activity
animal/plant	taking care of animals & planting seeds/collecting things in nature
tinkering	tinkering with mechanical and/or electrical devices
chemistry (chem)	engaging in chemistry
group	participation in science groups or clubs
comp	participation in sciene competitions
prog	writing computer programs and/or web pages
reading	reading/watching science fiction and/or non-fiction science
video (vid)	playing video games
talk	talking to family and/or peers about science
stars	observing stars

Figure 16: Full list of OST activities examined in this study. The leftmost column is the abbreviated variable name - names which will be used throughout the duration of this thesis for brevity. The rightmost column is the full explanation of the activity.

Figure 17: Percent of male participation vs. percent of female participation plotted for each of the 13 OST activities in the OPSCI survey. Each activity has 6 plotted points for the six different grade levels examined in the survey: K-4, 5-8, 9, 10, 11, and 12. Since student age is represented on neither axis, the point on each line indicating K-4 interest levels is denoted by a triangle with a back outline. The point indicating grade 12 interest levels is denoted by a circle with a black outline. The points in between follow chronologically. The black line indicates slope = 1, which is where all of the data points would lie if each activity were equally enjoyed by male and female students across all ages. Clearly, more males participate in video games and engineering-related activities (tinkering) regardless of age, and more females plant seeds and collect things from nature. In fact, most activities are skewed towards male students, including talking to family and peers about science, which has been proven in previous research to greatly affect female interest in STEM.

Figure 18: Percent of male participation vs. percent of female participation plotted for 2 OST activities of particular interest (see Section 5.2).

5 Analysis and Results

5.1 STEM Inflows

Building off of the results from the Sankey diagrams, we wanted to further analyze where astronomy students come from. Specifically, we decided to focus on the interval between the beginning and end of high school, and the common paths students take during that time on the road to the study of astronomy or STEM in general. To do this, we graphed the percentage of students who are interested in pursuing a career in STEM at the end of high school given a particular beginning of high school interest, as shown in Figure 19. Fields on the left side of the graph up to and including “Social Science” are classified as non-STEM, while fields to the right are considered STEM fields. We see that female STEM interest is lower across the board than male STEM interest. Furthermore, of students interested in astronomy in the beginning of high school, the percent of boys who stay in STEM is 22% higher than the percent of girls who stay in STEM. This is the second largest gender gap out of all BHS STEM interests. The largest gender gap occurs in computer science where the percent of boys who stay in STEM is 23% higher than the percent of girls.

We also analyzed the likelihood of a student ending up interested in astronomy specifically given a particular BHS interest. There was not enough data to demonstrate statistically significant results when the data was divided by gender, but the overall results are still of interest. Figure 20 is a graph of the percent of students interested in astronomy during EHS given any specific BHS interest. The error bars on this graph were still large, and thus we simplified the analysis to EHS astronomy interest as dependent on BHS interest in astronomy, STEM, STEM-related fields, or non-STEM, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 19: Graph depicting the percent of students interested in STEM at EHS given that they were interested in the specified BHS interest along the x-axis. Blue dots represent female participants, red represents male. The four horizontal black lines represent the average values for percent of students with EHS astronomy interest, divided into four categories: females with BHS non-STEM interest, males with BHS non-STEM interest, females with BHS STEM interest, and males with BHS STEM interest. We see that female interest in STEM is lower across the board than male STEM interest at the end of high school.

5.2 Statistical Models

With this initial understanding in place, we then began statistical modeling of the data in order to quantitatively determine which factors have the greatest influence on astronomy interest for male and female students. Figure 23 shows the results of two different logistic regression models. Each model works with the same dependent variable - EHS astronomy interest. Initially, we tested for effects by control variables including MS astronomy interest, BHS astronomy interest, BHS STEM interest, if the student took high school calculus, if

Figure 20: Graph depicting the percent of students interested in astronomy at EHS given that they were interested in the specified BHS interest along the x-axis. Male and female data are combined. We see a relatively high correlation with BHS astronomy and BHS physics.

the student took high school physics, number of years of mathematics, number of years of physics, number of years of science, SAT math score, and gender. These explanatory variables were chosen based on previous publications on similar subject matter (Sadler et al., 2012). Upon finding very low significance for many of the aforementioned variables, such as if the student took physics/calculus and their SAT math score, we examined correlation matrix for these variables to check for collinearity (Figure 22) and found high correlations to exist between “tookphys” and “yearsphys”, “tookphys” and “years science”, “yearsphys” and “years science”, and “satmath” and “yearsmath”. We therefore concluded that only “tookphys”, “tookcalc”, and “satmath” were necessary for the model. These three variables,

Figure 21: Graph depicting the percent of students interested in astronomy at EHS given that they were interested in either astronomy, STEM, STEM-related fields, or non-STEM during BHS. Male and female data are combined.

along with MS astronomy, BHS astronomy, BHS STEM, and gender are included in Model 1. In Model 2, we included main effects from the 8 OST factors, as combined via factor analysis in Figure 15. Only four of the eight proved initially significant: “tinkering”, “chemistry”, “stars”, and “talk”. Using what we gleaned from Models 1 and 2, we were able to construct Model 3, our final main effects model, as shown in Figure 24. It is noteworthy that Model 3 does not include control variables for the students’ physics and math background or their SAT math score, as such factors have proven significant in the pursuit of other STEM fields in the literature (Sadler et al., 2012; Dabney et al., 2012). Their lack of effect on astronomy career interest is surprising and informative.

Model 3 shows that students have greater odds of EHS astronomy interest if they have

BHS astronomy interest, BHS STEM interest, or participate in “stars”, and/or “talk”. Students have a statistically significant decrease in odds of EHS astronomy interest if they participate in “chemistry”, which we speculate likely leads students towards an interest in chemistry instead. To better quantify these effects, we calculated odds ratios corresponding to each explanatory variable, as shown in Figure 24. Odds ratios for Model 3 are generally equal to e^β where β is the regression coefficient. The odds ratio in Figure 24 highlighted in blue is shown as $1/e^\beta$ in order to keep all odds ratios greater than 1. We see from these calculations several notable results. Students who are interested in BHS astronomy have 18 times higher odds of EHS astronomy interest than those who are not. Similarly, the odds of a student with BHS STEM interest having EHS astronomy interest are almost twice as high as those of a student not interested in BHS STEM (1.8:1). Male students have 1.4 times higher odds of EHS astronomy interest when compared to females. Students who like to observe stars have 2.2:1 odds in favor of EHS astronomy interest compared to those who do not, and students who talk to their peers and family about science have 1.6:1 odds for the same. Students who participate in extracurricular chemistry have 1.4 times *worse* odds of having EHS astronomy interest than those who do not.

Variables	tookcalc	tookphys	yearsphys	yearsmath	yearsscience	satmathlin
tookcalc		0.063	0.070	0.063	0.103	0.055
tookphys	0.063		0.892	0.228	0.569	0.254
yearsphys	0.070	0.892		0.243	0.706	0.264
yearsmath	0.063	0.228	0.243		0.264	0.328
yearsscience	0.103	0.569	0.706	0.264		0.234
satmathlin	0.055	0.254	0.264	0.328	0.234	
<i>Values in bold are different from 0 with a significance level alpha=0.05</i>						

Figure 22: Correlations for the control variables “tookcalc”, “tookphys”, “yearsphys”, “years science”, and “satmathlin” (linearized SAT math score). High (> 0.5) correlations occur between “tookphys” and “yearsphys”, “tookphys” and “years science”, “yearsphys” and “years science”, and “satmath” and “yearsmath”. These correlations are highlighted in pink. All correlations are significant at the $p=0.05$ level.

After determining a final main effects regression model, we investigated potential interactions between explanatory variables. We found that the only significant effect occurs

Model Variable	Model 1 - Controls				Model 2 - OST Activities			
	β	sig.	p-value	SE	β	sig.	p-value	SE
msastro	0.534		0.064	0.289				
bhsastro	2.710	***	0.000	0.258	2.915	***	0.000	0.171
bhsstem	0.569	**	0.009	0.217	0.578	***	0.000	0.157
took calculus	1.138		0.058	0.600				
took physics	0.068		0.755	0.218				
SAT math (per 100pts)	-0.056		0.514	0.086				
gender (male)	0.185		0.391	0.216	0.265		0.103	0.163
tinkering					0.468	*	0.025	0.209
animal/plant					-0.415		0.063	0.223
vidgames/reading					-0.025		0.927	0.275
comp/group					0.060		0.727	0.172
chemistry					-0.375	*	0.028	0.171
programming					-0.176		0.303	0.171
stars					0.813	***	0.000	0.197
talk					0.497	*	0.011	0.195
R ²	0.1382				0.1746			

Figure 23: Logistic regression models predicting EHS astronomy interest in STATA. Control variables are labelled as follows: “bhsastro” indicates beginning of high school interest in astronomy, “bhsstem” indicates beginning of high school interest in STEM in general, “took calculus” is a binary variable indicating if they have taken any high school calculus, “took physics” is identical for physics, “SAT math” is the student’s linearized SAT math score. Model 2 also includes explanatory variables from OST activities. The explanatory variables that proved to be statistically significant are maintained in our final models (see Figure 24).

between gender and “stars”. The odds ratios corresponding to this interaction are shown numerically in Figure 25 and graphically in Figure 26. These ratios reveal that male students who do “star” have slightly (1.13:1) better odds of pursuing EHS astronomy than female students who do “star”, and males who do not do “star” have 2.74:1 odds of pursuing EHS astronomy when compared to females who do not do “star”. Males who participate in “star” have 1.58 times greater odds of EHS astronomy interest than males who do not, and females who participate in “star” have 3.8 times higher odds of EHS astronomy interest than females who do not. The odds ratio for the female students (those who do “star” vs. those who don’t) is therefore more than twice the odds ratio for the male students. This reveals that participation in “star” can work to bridge the gender gap in astronomy interest, as the career choice of females is much more sensitive to participation in “star” than that of males.

Another interesting result is that there was *no* interaction between gender and “talk” -

the other positive, significant main effect OST activity. This lack of interaction reveals that male and female students can confer the same benefit from talking to peers and family about science.

Model Variable	Model 3 - Main Effects					Model 4 - Interactions			
	β	sig.	p-value	SE	Odds ratio	β	sig.	p-value	SE
bhsastro	2.894	***	0.000	0.170	18.074	2.912	***	0.000	0.170
bhsstem	0.595	**	0.000	0.156	1.813	0.590	***	0.000	0.156
gender (male)	0.362	*	0.019	0.155	1.437	1.008	***	0.001	0.311
chemistry	-0.342	*	0.033	0.160	1.407	-0.344	*	0.031	0.160
stars	0.795	***	0.000	0.185	2.214	1.338	***	0.000	0.302
talk	0.463	*	0.012	0.184	1.589	0.462	*	0.012	0.184
gender-stars						-0.882	*	0.013	0.357
R ²	0.1706					0.1737			

Figure 24: Final statistical models for the dependent variable ‘EHS astronomy interest’. Model 3 - the main effects logistic regression - shows that students who have BHS astronomy interest, BHS STEM interest, are male, participate in “stars”, and/or participate in “talk” have increased likelihood for EHS astronomy interest. Model 4 shows the sole significant interaction effect, which occurs with gender and “stars”.

Male w/ star : Female w/ star	1.13 : 1
Male w/o star : Female w/o star	2.74 : 1
Male w/ star : Male w/o star	1.58 : 1
Female w/ star : Female w/o star	3.81 : 1

Figure 25: Odds ratios for the interaction effect in Model 4. Male students who do “star” have slightly (1.13:1) better odds of pursuing EHS astronomy than female students who do “star”, and males who do not do “star” have 2.74:1 odds of pursuing EHS astronomy when compared to females who do not do “star”. Males who participate in “star” have 1.58 times greater odds of EHS astronomy interest than males who do not, and females who participate in “star” have 3.8 times higher odds of EHS astronomy interest than females who do not. The odds ratio for the female students is therefore more than twice the odds ratio for the male students.

6 Discussion

The findings described above reveal an abundance of uncharted information on factors that affect the retention of astronomy students and the evolution of their career interests, particularly with respect to gender. In Figure 19 we see that STEM interest is lower across the

Figure 26: Histogram representing the odds ratios for the interaction effect in Model 4. Of the students who do not observe stars, males have much higher (2.74:1) odds of pursuing astronomy than females. However, of the students who *do* observe stars, males and females have comparable odds of pursuing astronomy (1.13:1).

board for female students when compared to male students, confirming that despite progress in recent years there is still a prominent gender gap in science and related fields. We also support the findings of Sadler et al. (2011), which stated that the largest gender gaps occur in astronomy and computer science (see Section 5.1). Furthermore, the field of astronomy experiences the most extreme and constant decrease in student interest of all fields spanning MS to college, as shown in Figures 2 and 4, a decrease that is stronger for females. This reveals that the majority of STEM education publications which do not consider the field of astronomy are remiss, as astronomy exemplifies not only the STEM retention issue in general, but also the retention of women in science.

Through the creation of Sankey diagrams to depict inflows and outflows of astronomy students, we concluded that for male students, and to a lesser extent females, there is a large out-

flow from astronomy into other STEM fields (Figures 9 & 10). A lower percentage of women than men remain in STEM, instead often moving into STEM-related (Health/Medicine) or non-STEM disciplines, as shown in Figure 14. These findings contribute to the often-used “leaky pipeline” metaphor (Riegle-Crumb, Moore, & Ramos-Wada, 2010; Sadler et al., 2011), which asserts that large numbers of students, particularly females, begin their education with interest in STEM but are lost at various stages along the way. Astronomy serves to combat this phenomenon by providing a pathway to hook students into other STEM fields. Moreover, when interpreting the outflows from astronomy to other STEM fields it is important to keep in mind the relatively low participation in astronomy overall. Although it is exciting that students interested in astronomy often feed into other STEM fields, astronomy student outflows still make up only a small percentage of the total STEM population.

In our statistical models, we found that the OST activities (such as “talk”, “star”, and “chem”) had larger effect sizes than variables depicting academic preparation (such as if the student took high school physics and their SAT math score) in influencing students’ decisions to pursue astronomy at the end of high school (Figure 23). This makes sense in light of past findings (Shettle, 2005; Riegle-Crumb, 2012) which state that over time both male and female students are taking more math and science courses in high school, and that female students are obtaining higher high school math and science GPAs than males on average. Taking this to be true, it would make sense that measures of academic preparation (courses taken, SAT score) are not significant predictors of astronomy interest.

Our findings on the importance of OST activities are interesting in light of popular theories on STEM retention, particularly for girls. As discussed in Section 2.1, two common hypotheses for the deficiency of female scientists are that women prefer people-oriented careers that do not conflict with family life (Diekman et al., 2010; Sadler et al., 2011), or that there is a lack of opportunities and support for female scientists (Xu, 2008). Although we neither support nor refute these theories with our research, we do introduce a new element

into the discussion. This element is *personal* engagement with science. In the case of astronomy, we see that students who spend extracurricular time observing stars and/or talking to peers and family about science have increased odds of EHS astronomy interest, regardless of gender. In fact, female students who engage in “stars” have a greater improvement in their odds of EHS astronomy interest than males do (Figure 26). This interaction between gender and “stars” is also interesting in light of findings by Sadler et al. (2011) which state that female students often feel less welcome in science-related groups and clubs. This creates a tension between the benefits of OST science and the barriers deterring student participation. This may be where talking to peers and family comes in – if students receive enough encouragement to engage in OST science activities, will the rate of participation increase? How much benefit will this confer towards increasing STEM interest in general and bridging the STEM gender gap?

The benefits of OST activities had been examined to some extent in past research, but never so directly as with this study. Our results build on the conclusions of Christensen et al. (2014) who demonstrated that a self-directed, interactive science education helps bridge the gender gap in science interest as well as increase retention in the short term (6th to 8th grades). However, this study only examined manifestations of self-directed science education within classroom confines. We broaden these conclusions to demonstrate the significance of self-directed scientific exploration outside of the classroom. We also extend the temporal effect of these activities through to end of high school interest. Some work has previously been done to examine benefits of activities outside of the classroom (Bergin, 1996; Guberman, 2004), but these activities were limited to those which directly improved classroom skills such as note taking and underlining texts. With this new study, we answer Bergin’s plea for an examination of less academic hobbies.

In 2011, Dabney et al. found OST science activities to be a key factor involved with university interest in STEM, but the study was limited in that it was unable to discern if

OST activities were a result or precursor to STEM interest. We herein show that two OST activities (“star” and “talk”) are significant predictors of EHS astronomy interest.

One possible explanation for the benefits we see from OST activities is that extracurricular, self-directed participation in science-related activities improves students’ personal identification with scientific subjects. This would align with the findings of Hazari et al. (2010, 2013), which state that discussing the underrepresentation of women in science (an activity highly reminiscent of “talk” in the OPSCI data) had significant positive effects on the retention of STEM females. In this way, such OST activities may also inform a student’s sense of “gender-STEM compatibility”, a concept shown to affect students’ gender rejection sensitivity and consequently their persistence in STEM (Ahlqvist, 2013). Furthermore, having taken counsel from papers by Hazari et al., we were right to leave “talk” as its own explanatory variable rather than combining it with other OST activities through factor analysis, as it proved to be significant on its own.

6.1 Limitations and Future Research

The data used in this study, as obtained through the OPSCI survey (n=15,848), included responses from hundreds of students interested in astronomy. That being said, this number is still much smaller than the proportions of surveyed students interested in other STEM fields. Were we able to survey a larger sample of astronomy students, we might have been able to do more detailed analyses on the difference between patterns undertaken by male and female students. For example, it may be interesting in the future to expand upon Figures 20 and 21 to show the percents of male vs. female students interested in astronomy at the end of high school given a specific beginning of high school interest.

This study has shown that OST activities such as “talk”, “stars”, and “chem” have a more significant influence on students’ interest in astronomy at the end of high school than

various academic measures, including previous math and science courses and SAT math score. In future research, however, it would be interesting to see a detailed, quantitative analysis of how the influences of OST activities and academic preparation compare for other STEM disciplines, particularly physics, which is an adjacent field to astronomy. It may also be interesting to broaden the inquiry to life sciences.

We have also shown that OST participation has an effect on student retention between the beginning and end of high school: students who enter high school interested in astronomy (or STEM in general) have much higher odds of pursuing astronomy at the end of high school (Figure 24). It follows that students who participate in middle school OST activities may experience a benefit that carries through high school and into college. This would require hierarchical modeling, which we did not engage for this study but could be advisable in future work.

Finally, this analysis measures effects on interest in astronomy, but does not analyze potential effects on academic performance. In future research, it would be of interest to examine how OST activities affect STEM performance, particularly at the college level.

7 Conclusions

In this study, we have demonstrated that students who engage in certain science-related, out-of-school time (OST) activities have higher odds for interest in pursuing the field of astronomy at the end of high school (EHS) when compared to students who do not participate. Specifically, students who observe stars extracurricularly and/or talk to their family and peers about science have improved odds of astronomy interest. Furthermore, there is an interaction effect between gender and observing stars, such that female students who observe stars experience a greater increase in odds of EHS astronomy interest than male students do. This has great implications for implementable change. The presence of after-

school programs and clubs geared towards observing stars could improve students' chances of pursuing astronomy at the end of high school. Moreover, astronomy programs (clubs, camps, one-night events) specifically geared towards girls may not only greatly accelerate their interest in astronomy – making their odds of pursuing astronomy comparable to those of the boys – but would likely be more amenable to the students' parents. Particularly for nighttime events conducive to astronomy, an all-girls event or club would likely gain parent support before a co-ed program. Furthermore, as we see in Figure 18, there is currently higher participation in “star” during grades 5 through 8 than during any year of high school, which is true of both male and female students. This suggests that there may be a greater need for observing programs for high school age students.

The other OST activity that demonstrated a significant effect on the retention of astronomy students is talking to family and peers about science (“talk”). This activity showed no interaction effect with gender, signifying that the activity confers equal benefit to boys and girls alike. However, the activity “talk” becomes increasingly male-dominated as students age (Figure 18). Parents and teachers should therefore spend more time talking to students about science, and make a concerted effort to engage in this behavior with female students as much as they do with males. This will allow male and female students to benefit equally, improving all students' odds of pursuing astronomy at the end of high school.

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